

Technical Assistance and Utilization of Self Learning Modules in the MAPEH Learning Area

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Abstract. The study aimed to assess the level of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and its relationship with the utilization of self-learning modules in music, arts, physical education, and health among Grade 6 teachers in Maco North District, Davao de Oro. Employing a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design, the respondents were Elementary-Level MAPEH Teachers from the Davao de Oro Schools Division. Data collection employed an adapted survey instrument, and analysis involved calculating means, standard deviations, Pearson r correlation, and linear regression. Results indicated that Davao de Oro schools demonstrated widespread technical support through coaching, guidance, and empowerment by school leaders and master teachers, reflecting effective management practices. Teachers' use of self-learning modules across MAPEH components was also pervasive. A significant positive correlation was found between the level of technical assistance and the extent of utilization of the self-learning module. Furthermore, coaching, guiding, and empowering each other showed a statistically significant influence on teachers' use of these modules. It was recommended that Public School District Supervisors in Davao de Oro consider other factors that could further enhance pedagogical practices related to self-learning modules, especially in alternative delivery modes, to inform future policy developments.

KEY WORDS

1. Technical Assistance
2. Self-Learning Modules
3. Music
4. Arts
5. Physical Education and Health

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1. Introduction

Technical assistance and the use of self-learning modules in MAPEH were vital for a comprehensive and effective teaching and learning process because they support teachers, enhance student engagement, and facilitate personalized learning. Technical support helps educators integrate innovative tools, while self-learning modules provide a structured approach for students to learn at their own pace, ensuring that the holistic benefits of Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health are realized, even in challenging learning environments. Technology-based teaching methods and self-learning materials offer numerous benefits for teachers and students. They enhance teaching capabilities, improve content delivery, and provide personalized learning for students. These methods enhance student motivation and participation in subjects like MAPEH, which are often perceived as less academically rigorous. They also

help develop essential skills such as communication, critical thinking, and self-confidence. Self-learning modules and technology were accessible to students with different abilities or in varied learning environments. They are crucial for holistic development, addressing learning gaps, and adapting to new paradigms. In the context of MAPEH, these tools help address the needs of struggling learners and ensure continuity in the teaching and learning process. In the Philippines, where modular distance learning is adopted, self-learning modules have been a primary method for maintaining continuity in teaching and learning. At the international, national, and local levels, the development and delivery of system-change initiatives in the areas of education, welfare, and health are supported with initiatives designed to build the capacity of individuals and organizations to achieve desired outcomes. However, given the key role technical assistance has in translating knowledge into policy, programs, and practice, there have been few attempts to identify critical components of successful T.A. and even fewer rigorous attempts to evaluate effectiveness. In the education parlance, notions of effective T.A. have incorporated principles from a variety of theoretical perspectives, including theories of change, adult learning, coaching, consultation, and facilitation. It is emphasized as engagement and thought to be grounded in a trusting, respectful working relationship characterized by reciprocal interaction and co-equal status. Second, the content and intensity should align with the recipient's unique needs and desired outcomes, allowing for mutual goal setting where the recipient assumes the leadership role in determining their needs and the methods to meet them (Olson et al., 2020). Maier (2022) reports that a growing number of states are launching community school initiatives to ensure family and community engagement, provide enriched and expanded learning opportunities, and offer integrated support for students. Several states are providing technical assistance to support the high-quality implementation of community schools, either through the state education agency or regional and local partners. This brief offers examples from the National Center for Community Schools and from New York, New Mexico, and California showing how technical assistance can build capacity through consultation, training, coaching, and knowledge building. Moreover, the third principle that underlies effective T.A. is awareness of the influences in the environment that affect the recipient's ability to benefit from support. Fourth, T.A. often emphasizes the importance of a structured approach by the provider, including the specification of measurable goals linked to concrete action steps, the provision of continuous feedback, the improvement of feedback loops, and the discussion of progress to track activities. Lastly, there is an emphasis on empowerment and motivation. This has led to the development of confidence, and efficacy is recognized as a fundamental ingredient in achieving positive outcomes (Kapur, 2018, as cited by Olson, 2020). In the Philippine setting, San Antonio (2020) noted that DepEd Teachers integrate technical assistance to improve the delivery of basic education services. The Department of Education launched DepEd Teachers, an online program featuring episodes that focus on steps and initiatives for overcoming the challenges in providing education in the new normal, during the mid-year In-Service Training (INSET) Week from December 14 to 18, 2020. The program aims to address confusion and doubts about the Department's curriculum, instruction, and assessment initiatives. This initiative is a contribution from the Curriculum and Instruction strand to support the Department of Education's efforts in communicating with various stakeholders. It serves as a mechanism for providing technical assistance to the field as we adapt to the new normal in basic education (Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones,

2020). Meanwhile, Assistant Secretary for Curriculum and Instruction Alma Ruby Torio tackled the focus of each “Overcoming Challenges” series, namely: curriculum, learning delivery modalities, classroom assessment, and learning resources. Directors Jocelyn Andaya, Leila Areola, Lito Palomar (OIC), and Ariz Delson Acay Cawilan (OIC) took turns discussing their respective topics (Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones, 2020). To create a community of practice on curriculum, instruction, and assessment issues, DepEd Teachers will run episodes featuring best practices from regional directors, school division superintendents, school principals, and teachers starting January 2021. Other educational experts will also be invited to give talks on current issues and trends in basic education. Much like the DepED Central office’s directives in implementing the T.A. process to simplify the substantiation of management and delivery of curriculum and instruction among schools’ beneficiaries, a gap has been observed in terms of decision-making, implementation, and evaluation in the provision of technical assistance. There are different experiences as observed in the implementation of the process when it is given to the respective learning areas. This created confusion and raised doubts among recipients about the proper execution of the process. At the School Level, it has been observed that in Schools in the Maco North District, TA has not been explicitly implemented. Thus, in the particular learning area of MAPEH Grade 6 (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health), teachers are having difficulty appreciating the delivery of the process given by the respective Master Teachers and School Heads to make effective delivery in the said learning area across quarter periods. It is at this juncture that this study is conceptualized, discussed, and proposed to generate results that would be appropriate for appreciation and implementation.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature— This section presents significant literature on

Technical Assistance (T.A.) in education, highlighting its definitions, practices, and applications from international and local contexts.

1.1.1. Concept of Technical Assistance— Technical Assistance refers to professional guidance and support aimed at improving organizational effectiveness and learning outcomes. Traditionally seen as supervising and monitoring, it has shifted toward coaching, guiding, and empowering stakeholders (Niepes, undated; Magcanas, 2019). It is a process that uses tools, skills, and collaborative planning to help schools solve problems, enhance performance, and achieve goals, aligned with RA 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001.

T.A. is often tailored to client needs and may be short-term (addressing specific skills) or long-term (supporting systemic reform). Effective T.A. emphasizes collaboration, adaptability, and accountability, ensuring that clients are supported while also empowered to pursue self-reliance (Blase, 2009; Dunst, 2019).

*1.1.2. Models and Practices—*A review of multiple frameworks identified five core components of T.A.: preparation, planning, implementation, evaluation, and sustainability (Dunst, 2019; Maier, 2021). Effective practices include classroom observation, coaching, and Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions to strengthen teacher competence and school-based management. Internationally, co-creation models highlight collaboration, trust, and tailoring support to specific contexts (Yazejian et al., 2019).

Studies emphasize that outcomes improve when T.A. is timely, context-specific, and collaborative (Olson, 2020; Marinenko, 2021). Positive effects are observed across system levels, from improved practitioner skills to better service access for families.

*1.1.3. Applications in Education—*In the Philippines, the Department of Education established Regional and Division Field Technical Assistance Divisions to support school-based management through relevant and timely inter-

ventions (Magcanas, 2019). Technical Assistance is central to BESRA and RA 9155, reinforcing decentralization and making schools the heart of the education system.

Globally, T.A. is also evident in higher education and community schools. Universities provide additional support for international students through simplified assignments, guidance, and intercultural engagement (Marinenko, 2021). Community schools in the U.S. integrate student support and family engagement, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Maier, 2020; Leung et al., 2021).

1.1.4. Evaluation and Outcomes—Evaluation is essential to determine T.A.’s effectiveness and guide continuous improvement (Leung et al., 2019). Effective T.A. is collaborative, systematic, targeted, adaptive, and results-driven, ultimately building organizational capacity and sustaining reforms (Lauer et al., 2014, as cited in Magcanas, 2019).

Overall, literature affirms that T.A. is a collaborative, flexible, and results-oriented process that supports school improvement and system reforms. Locally, it is vital for strengthening school-based management and teacher performance, while globally, it addresses diverse educational needs from community schools to higher education. Its success depends on being tailored, sustained, and continuously evaluated.

1.2. Synthesis—A significant relationship exists between technical assistance and the utilization of self-learning modules (SLMs) in MAPEH, as adequate technical support empowers teachers with the necessary skills and confidence to use these modules effectively, leading to improved student engagement and learning outcomes in the subject. Teachers who receive adequate technical assistance can better integrate technology and SLMs into their teaching, personalizing learning experiences and making the material more accessible and engaging for students. This support is crucial for fostering student success and ensuring that the educa-

tional goals of MAPEH are met, particularly in new learning modalities such as distance learning. Technical assistance enhances teachers’ proficiency and confidence in using technology and Self-Learning Modules (SLMs), thereby improving learning experiences and bridging skill gaps. It helps teachers create dynamic and engaging lessons that incorporate technology and multimedia. This support also enhances student outcomes, resulting in increased engagement and improved academic performance. Technical assistance is crucial for managing self-learning modules in distance learning contexts, maintaining educational continuity. It also serves as a form of professional development, helping educators continuously improve their pedagogical integration of technology and SLMs. Technical assistance for MAPEH teachers is crucial for enhancing teaching methods, increasing efficiency, bridging the gap, and facilitating the use of multimedia. It helps teachers adopt digital tools, create personalized learning plans, and enhance productivity and student engagement. Self-learning modules promote independent learning, developing self-study skills and a sense of responsibility for education. These modules can be contextualized to support specific learning needs, ensuring meaningful engagement and improved academic performance. Students become more empowered as they take ownership of their learning journey, which is especially beneficial for practical skills and knowledge required in MAPEH. Overall, technical assistance is essential for ensuring effective teaching and learning in MAPEH.

1.3. Theoretical and Conceptual Framework—The proposed study is grounded in the Technical Assistance Model theory, as authored by Le, Anthony, Bronheim, and Holland (2014). Accordingly, the authors described in their arguments that technical assistance (T.A.) has been a ubiquitous component of policy implementation across public and private enterprises for decades. There have been a few attempts to

identify critical components of T.A. and evaluate its effectiveness. A qualitative analysis of interviews with experienced T.A. providers has suggested a continuum of practice, anchored at each end by approaches termed content-driven and relationship-based. Moreover, content-driven approaches focus on information transfer and referral, whereas relationship-based approaches center on facilitating behavior and systems change. T.A. is almost always a mix of these approaches. Fitting the right approach to each situation is the key to success. The structure of T.A. is conceptualized as a three-phase set of activities (decision-making, implementation, and evaluation) supported by an effective partnership and informed by the overarching context. The strategies for effective T.A. are consistent with major theories of behavior change but need to be further evaluated and refined (Le et al., 2014). Moreover, Olson et al. (2020) noted that in recent years, T.A. provision has become a standard component of the implementation process for a wide variety of youth-focused federal, state, and community-based initiatives, spawning a small but growing body of literature focused on evaluating and identifying the characteristics of effective T.A. There has been growing interest in studying how to utilize training and T.A. to support the implementation of specific evidence-based practices, as well as an emerging dialogue about how best to use T.A. to improve the overall functioning of larger organizations and systems. Moreover, there has been consistent interest in ensuring that T.A. systems themselves are based on comparative effectiveness research. Furthermore, the authors noted that T.A. must be administered at a sufficient dosage. Recent evidence suggests that long-term, ongoing T.A. is asso-

ciated with better outcomes than a one-shot, time-limited effort. Second, TA should encompass a mixture of intensive support (e.g., on-site consultation and engagement in in-person and virtual learning communities) that provides opportunities for experiential learning through hands-on demonstrations and off-site check-ins via telephone and electronic communications, allowing for cost-efficient and frequent contacts. Third, TA activities benefit from a collaborative approach in which T.A. providers offer expert guidance in specific substantive areas and also form working relationships with various stakeholders, including policy-makers, program administrators, implementers, and service recipients. Finally, recent papers have suggested that there are benefits associated with a proactive approach to T.A., in which T.A. providers anticipate stakeholder needs and respond to those needs in a timely, positive, and ongoing way. Proactive TA typically builds upon stakeholder strengths with the ultimate goal of improved systems-level capacity and high-quality implementation (Olson et al., 2020). In this study, stakeholders primarily include the teachers who are the beneficiaries of the technical assistance provided by the Master Teachers and the School Heads. These processes aim to simplify steps for the learners of MAPEH Grade 6, facilitating the mastery of learning competencies. In this manner, the study has to adopt the phases of provision of technical assistance, namely the decision-making phase, implementation phase, and the evaluation phase, where these indicators are under independent variable – provision of technical assistance, while dependent variable self-learning modules utilization given components Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health are the respective indicators.

This study determined which among the provisions of T.A. phases can influence the level of utilization of the SLMs across MAPEH compo-

nents in the grade 6 level, as facilitated among teachers in Maco North, Davao de Oro.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

1.4. *Statement of the Problem*—The study was conducted to determine the extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and how it correlates with the level of self-learning module utilization in music, arts, physical education, and health in Grade 6 at Maco North District, Davao de Oro. This specifically sought to answer the following statement of the problem:

- (1) What is the extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in terms of;
 - (1) coaching;
 - (2) guiding;
 - (3) empowering
- (2) What is the extent of the self-learning modules utilization in MAPEH, in terms of;
 - (1) Music;
 - (2) Arts;
 - (3) Physical Education;
 - (4) Health;
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between the technical assistance provided by and self-learning module utilization in MAPEH?
- (4) Which among the domains of technical assistance significantly influence the extent of self-learning module utilization in MAPEH?

1.5. *Hypotheses*—To provide empirical evidence given the posed theoretical and conceptual frameworks as claimed by the study, null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 alpha level of significance, stating: Ho 1: There is no significant relationship between the technical assistance provided by and self-learning module utilization in MAPEH 6. And, Ho 2: None of the domains of technical assistance significantly influences the extent of self-learning module utilization in MAPEH 6. The proposed given data, analysis, interpretations, and implications for the real world. The reflections on possible results would provide sound outputs for the school’s stakeholders and the broader learning community, facilitating cyclical planning and informed decision-making. This study outlined the terms that are conceptually and operationally defined to establish a better understanding and reference when discussing the results in the preceding chapters of the study. Provision of Technical Assistance. The term refers to the most important ways to provide technical

assistance through classroom observation, learning action cell (LAC) sessions, and individual coaching. In those three areas, teachers' weaknesses are being addressed and strengthened to meet the diverse needs of their learners. In this study, the provision of T.A. calls for the School Heads and Master Teachers of Maco North to extend their mentoring and coaching to address difficulties in the facilitation of learning competencies in MAPEH Grade 6 across the grading period of S.Y. 2021-2022. Self-Learning Modules Utilization. The term refers to the proper utilization of Self-learning modules (SLMs) for

learners' portfolio assessment (DO14, S 2012). The Department issued DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2012 titled, "Policy and Guidelines on the Proper Distribution, Care, Recording, Retrieval and Disposal of Text Books (TXs) along with the Teachers Manuals (T.M.s) and Other Instructional Materials (IMS) in order to improve access to the mentioned materials, maximize their use and minimize or eliminate damages and/or losses. In this study, utilization refers to and includes the components in MAPEH Grades 6, namely, Music, Arts, PE, and Health, across grading periods for S.Y. 2021-2022.

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the narratives of the methodical process involved in conducting the study. This includes the design of the study, the respondents and their sampling method, the research instruments to be used in data gathering, the procedure, the ethical considerations, and, lastly, the data analysis. These steps are considered essential to assume appropriateness and correctness in the conduct of the methodical steps.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed a non-experimental, descriptive-correlational, and predictive research design. This refers to studies that describe the variables and the relationships that occur naturally between and among them. Furthermore, the study variables are classified into independent (predictor) and dependent (outcome) categories. Moreover, any scientific process begins with a description, based on observation, of an event or events, from which theories may later be developed to explain the observations (Pallant, 2020). On the other hand, Predictive research is chiefly concerned with predicting outcomes, consequences, costs, or effects. This type of research attempts to extrapolate from the analysis of existing phenomena, policies, or other entities to predict something that has not been tried, tested, or proposed before (Gujarati, 2020). In this study, indicators under the independent variable of the study, Provision of Technical Assistance, namely, coaching, guiding, and empowering,

which School Heads and Master Teachers render, are supposed to be correlated with the level of utilization of Self-learning Modules for MAPEH Grade 6 concerning each component, namely, Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health. Using the design mentioned, it is assumed that the variables under study, along with the indicators mentioned, will enable the researcher to empirically provide evidence that the presented hypothesis is null and void.

2.2. Research Respondents—Respondents of the proposed study were the Elementary Level MAPEH Teachers of the Davao de Oro Schools Division. Using the Raosoft sample size calculator, a total of 120 respondents were randomly selected from each of the respective elementary schools. One randomly selected respondent will be informed through an online platform and, considering the availability of Wi-Fi connections, may also be oriented face-to-face. They will be informed about the purpose and importance of the study. As much as pos-

sible, these respondents are handling MAPEH Grade 6, as well, and how they function and contribute to the learning outcomes given the new standard learning system during S.Y. 2020-2021. The ethics of research and the process of collecting survey responses were explicitly discussed with the respondents, and the observance of health protocols was strictly enforced based on Executive Order 31, S. 2020, to prevent possible contamination and reduce the risk of infection.

2.3. *Research Instruments*—This proposed research study used a self-made survey instrument. Items were adapted from the types of literature reviewed and the content derived from preliminary interviews and narratives with colleagues, which were found to be relevant to the reviews. There are two parts, which consist of the extent of technical assistance provided

by the School Heads and Master Teachers, and where indicators are taken from the principles of curriculum and instruction in school-based management. On the other hand, the second part of the survey is the level of utilization of the self-learning modules concerning MAPEH Grade 6 components, namely music, arts, physical education, and health. The survey statements underwent a test-retest analysis to assess validity and reliability, using Cronbach’s Alpha at a 0.05 level of confidence, which yielded a coefficient of 0.857. This indicates a high positive correlation among the constructs. (Pallant 2010). The questionnaire employed a 5-point Likert scale to assess the extent of technical assistance and the utilization of SLMs in MAPEH at the Davao de Oro Schools Division. Scale, descriptive rating, and interpretation are provided below:

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of technical assistance is always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of technical assistance is oftentimes manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of technical assistance is sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of technical assistance is rarely manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of technical assistance is not manifested

Meanwhile, to determine the extent of utilization of SLMs in the MAPEH Learning area,

a 5-point Likert scale was used in this study, as presented below;

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The extent of utilization of SLMs in the MAPEH Learning area is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The extent of utilization of SLMs in the MAPEH Learning area is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The extent of utilization of SLMs in the MAPEH Learning area is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The extent of utilization of SLMs in the MAPEH Learning area is rarely manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The extent of SLMs’ utilization in the MAPEH Learning area is not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Permission to conduct the study. The research study adhered to the ethical procedures for data collection as outlined in IATF policy. After the panel and dean approved the research proposal, the researcher obtained permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro and the local barangays to collect data in the schools. Distribution and retrieval of the questionnaire. The research team created a Google Sheet form for an online survey, distributing it to randomly selected respondents via email. For those without internet access, hard copies were provided. The survey was conducted from March 21 to 28, 2022, with responses collected until mid-April. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires continued in April and May 2022, followed by data collation and analysis under the guidance of the Thesis Adviser. Collation and statistical treatment of data. The results of the preliminary analysis were then presented to the thesis adviser for guidance on interpreting and drawing implications from the study, as well as for further refining the analysis to enhance the meaning of the interpretations.

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Proper authorization and consent were obtained from the study respondents to ensure that all their rights were fully protected, specifically in the handling of their data. The profile of the respondents in the study was kept confidential to protect their rights, especially since the respondents were minors. This study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring that the data could not be traced back to the participants, who were the primary source of information, thereby protecting the respondents' identities. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the respondents' consent. Thus, access was limited to the researcher alone to ensure that no personal data would be exposed. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher was the only person who could access the survey results. After

the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently destroyed the survey results to ensure that the data could not be traced back to the respondents, who were the natural source of the information. The researcher also considers this to mean protecting the data from disclosure to unauthorized individuals or groups. Conversely, privacy relates more to participants' control over the extent and manner of sharing personal information. The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study. Hence, in adherence to the policy set by the University of Mindanao's ethics committee, corresponding requirements were strictly followed to ensure the appropriateness of the process based on the standards, thus mitigating possible risks such as physical, psychological, and socio-economic effects that were avoided.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The analysis involved calculating the Mean Scores and Standard Deviations to examine the extent of technical assistance provided by school heads and master teachers, as well as the level of utilization of self-learning modules for MAPEH Grade 6. To explore the relationship between these variables, Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r) was employed, allowing for an assessment of both the strength and direction of the association between the extent of technical support and the degree of self-learning module utilization in the subject area. Furthermore, a linear regression analysis was conducted to identify which specific indicators of technical assistance have a significant impact on the level of self-learning module utilization in MAPEH Grade 6. This approach helps pinpoint the key factors that influence how well students utilize the modules, aligning with the frameworks outlined by Pallant (2000) and Gujarati (2000). All statistical procedures were performed using JASP version 0.12.20, a software designed for comprehensive data analysis and statistical inference. The subsequent discussion interprets

the findings, providing insights into the relationships and influences identified through the statistical tests, which can inform strategies for enhancing technical support and optimizing the use of self-learning modules in this educational context.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered through tabular and textual forms, laying the groundwork for a clear understanding and information on the queries based on the statement of the problem posed. The implications of the results are presented through various reviews, which corroborate and argue the hypothesis and theory as claimed and posed in the study.

3.1. Extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers— Technical Assistance is any form of professional help, guidance, or support to enhance the effectiveness of their functions. It is an active process with steps to follow; it utilizes tools, involves process consultation, requires specific skills, and focuses on achieving set goals. It is also a journey, reminding the client of their primary responsibility and accountability, while respecting their capabilities and pace. The traditional concept of TA encompasses supervising, monitoring, evaluating, directing, and instructing. However, in the new paradigm, it is more on Coaching, Guiding, and Empowering. Teaching the subject matter was the primary focus of the conventional way of monitoring. However, now, all aspects of Education Management are given importance, highlighting the Provision of Access, Quality, and Relevance, as well as the Provision and Improvement of management services. As accentuated in Republic Act 9155, which is the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, “The State shall encourage local initiatives for improving the quality of basic education.”

Table 1. Extent of Technical Assistance Provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in Terms of Coaching

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Facilitates the conduct of situation analysis based on quarterly results	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Finds possible root cause and qualifies for planning	4.21	Very Extensive
3	Assesses possible solution from among the developed interventions	4.31	Very Extensive
4	Maps the least learned competencies among components	4.44	Very Extensive
5	Conducts consultation between and among teachers on pedagogical needs for enhancement	4.21	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.27	Very Extensive

Table 1 shows the responses on the extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers. It can be depicted that in terms of coaching, extent of technical assistance provision was very extensive in terms of mapping least learned competencies among components (4.44); assessing possible solution from among the developed interventions (4.31); finding possible root cause and qualifies for planning (4.21); conducting consultation between

and among teachers on pedagogical needs for enhancement (4.21) and facilitating the conduct of situation analysis based on quarterly results (4.20). It can be deduced that coaching in providing TA delivered by School Heads and Master Teachers was very extensive in their practices. Coaching was a form of development in which an experienced person, called a coach, supports a learner or client in achieving a specific personal or professional goal by providing training and guidance. The essence of coaching is to help a person change in the way they wish and help them go in the direction they want to go. Coaching supports individuals at every level in becoming who they aspire to be. Coaching builds awareness, empowers choice, and leads to change. The primary purpose of coaching is to maximize performance by helping clients reach their peak potential. The primary purpose of coaching involves developing leadership, fostering self-discipline, establishing a self-belief system, generating motivation, and enhancing self-awareness. Schools were an evidence-based strategy to advance a "whole child" approach to education by offering integrated student supports, expanded and enriched learning time, family and community engagement, and collaborative leadership and practices. In these current times, coaching is essential and must have a strategy to remain more relevant

than ever during the COVID-19 pandemic. By providing a well-coordinated and comprehensive set of supports, even in a distance learning environment, community schools can help address the digital divide and provide essential services such as food delivery and healthcare (Maier, 2020). Moreover, since the COVID-19 pandemic emerged in the United States in March 2020, districts nationwide have faced the challenging task of reopening schools safely and keeping them open. It was beneficial to learn from the successes of districts that have employed multilayered mitigation strategies to mitigate the risk of in-school transmission. The San Diego County Office of Education has mobilized technical assistance, leveraged partnerships, and gathered data to support districts as they navigated initial school closures, distance learning, and planning for reopening (Leung et al., 2021). According to Green (2021), effective teacher leaders, similar to master teachers, embody three key themes: facilitating professional development within their schools, actively participating in school-wide decision-making processes, and enhancing student achievement and success. This suggests that when offering instructional support through coaching, a collaborative community of pedagogical experts must work together to achieve desired outcome indicators.

Table 2. Extent of Technical Assistance Provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in Terms of Guiding

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Organize possible interventions for effective solutions	4.22	Very Extensive
2	Tracks and assesses performance among teachers	4.24	Very Extensive
3	Coaches and mentors per week for follow-up performance	4.50	Very Extensive
4	Monitors closely in the delivery based on the agreed strategies	4.34	Very Extensive
5	Checks and balances possible entries as anticipation for adjustments of interventions	4.45	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.35	Very Extensive

Table 2 presents the extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in terms of guiding. It can be seen that a very extensive actualization of guiding in terms of coaching and mentoring the teachers per week for follow up performance (4.50); checking and balancing possible entries as anticipation for adjustments of interventions (4.45); monitoring closely in the delivery based on the agreed strategies (4.34); tracking and assessing performance among teachers (4.24) and organizing possible interventions for effective solutions (4.22). This implies that management in schools is practicing a very extensive provision of technical assistance to teachers. Guiding means to direct in a course or show the way to be followed; guide implies intimate knowledge of the way and of all its difficulties and dangers. Guiding principles are a management method in which company leaders can directly demonstrate the principles that they want employees to follow for a better workplace. In this context, DepEd Caraga has established the Regional Field Technical Assistance Composite Teams (RFTACTs), comprising team leaders and members from cross-functional divisions. The RFTACTs monitor the implementation of various programs and projects using a corresponding monitoring tool designed to assess the implementation of specific programs or projects. Prior to the field monitoring visits, FTAD formulates a TA Plan that stipulates all activities

Empowerment means you're transferring power to someone else. You think someone else needs you, and your permission, your influence, your talents to do something. Empowerment was a means to include the team in decision-making, giving them a participatory role that capitalizes on their own expertise and judgment, and increases their sense of both individual worth and commitment to the organization. The most important ways of providing

and strategies to guide RFTACT members on their roles and responsibilities during and after the monitoring, along with the reports to be completed. It is expected that RFTACT members should be conversant with the various programs and projects and should delve deeper into understanding the situations of the school divisions, their needs, aspirations, strengths, and weaknesses in order to provide appropriate and relevant technical assistance. Correspondingly, an exit conference will be held to inform the Schools Division Superintendents of the findings, observations, and recommendations aimed at improving the schools' performance and helping them achieve their goals and targets. In a nutshell, TA is provided to solve problems, improve performance, and get results (Niepes, undated). Table 3 presents the responses of the technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in terms of empowering. It can be seen that empowerment exhibits very extensive in terms of appreciating implications as potential performance for next step plans (4.49); backing track of assessment results and injected interventions for effective feedback (4.41); reviewing solutions and adjustments interventions (4.34); analyzing results and interprets implications (4.24) and collecting results and considers potential data (4.20). This implies that School Heads and Master Teachers are extensive in their provision of TA through empowerment.

technical assistance are through classroom observation, learning action cell (LAC) sessions, and individual guidance. In those three areas where teachers' weaknesses are being strengthened and improved to address the diverse needs of their learners. School principals exercise significant influence on teacher professional development. There are four areas where principals have the opportunity to have a substantial impact on teacher learning. These include serving

Table 3. Extent of Technical Assistance Provided by School Heads and Master Teachers in Terms of Empowering

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Collects results and considers potential data	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Analyzes results and interprets implications	4.24	Very Extensive
3	Reviews solutions and adjustments to interventions	4.34	Very Extensive
4	Back tracks assessment results and injected interventions for effective feedback	4.41	Very Extensive
5	Appreciates implications as potential performance for next step plans	4.49	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.33	Very Extensive

as a principal instructional leader and learner; creating a learning environment; directly involving oneself in the design, delivery, and content of professional development; and assessing professional development outcomes. The most important responsibility of every educator is to provide the conditions under which people’s learning curves go off the chart. Whether one is called a principal, a teacher, a professor, a foundation official, or a parent, our most vital work is promoting human learning. The focus of analysis was on generally agreed-upon

technical assistance practices that were considered essential for planning, implementing, and evaluating the effectiveness of technical assistance (Blase, 2009, as cited by Magcanas, 2019). Table 4 provides information on the extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master teachers in terms of coaching (4.27), guiding (4.35), and empowerment (4.33). It can be deduced that a very extensive exhibition of technical assistance is provided by School Heads and Master Teachers.

Table 4. Summary on the Extent of Technical Assistance Provided by School Heads and Master Teachers

No.	Indicators	Mean	DI
1	Coaching	4.27	Very Extensive
2	Guiding	4.35	Very Extensive
3	Empowering	4.33	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.31	Very Extensive

Technical assistance was, in essence, a process for developing creative, cost-effective ways to provide targeted support to an organization, system, or individual to: Assess gaps, barriers, and needs and identify potential responses to address these issues; Develop a strategic plan for long-term change; or create an innovative approach to an emerging complex issue.

3.2. *Extent of the Self-Learning Modules Utilization in MAPEH*—Self-learning modules

were designed to allow learners to choose what to learn, how to learn, when to learn, and where to learn. This flexibility was a crucial characteristic of the open learning process. The results of most studies indicate that both methods of teaching, i.e., traditional and self-learning modules, enhance process skills among students. However, teaching through self-learning modules is more effective than the traditional method, as it results in significantly higher gains in process

skills. Self-paced learning enables students to have control over the location, time, and pace of their learning, and this increased autonomy can lead to improved motivation. Additionally, it can result in reduced staffing costs through a decrease in the amount of teacher-student contact.

Table 5. Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization in Music

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Distributes SLM for Music Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Provides extra worksheets and supplemental learning materials necessary for Music Grade 6 competencies per quarter	4.24	Very Extensive
3	Ensures collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished	4.34	Very Extensive
4	Provides feedback based on the learner’s performance immediately on the following week	4.41	Very Extensive
5	Appreciates learner’s performance on Music learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings	4.49	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.33	Very Extensive

Table 5 shows the extent of self-learning module utilization in Music. This can be seen that a pervasive utilization by Teachers in Music Learning component in MAPEH in terms of appreciating learner’s performance on Music learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings (4.49); providing feedback based on the learner’s performance immediately on the following week (4.41); ensuring that collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished (4.34); providing extra work sheets and supplemental learning materials necessary for Music Grade 6 competencies per quarter (4.24) and distributing SLM for Music Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter (4.20). The main challenges that the students have encountered include self-studying, poor internet connection, lack of sleep, and insufficient time to complete all the modules due to the large number of activities, distractions, and lack of focus. The following are the positive effects of modular learning on students. It helped students econo-

mize on daily transportation, fares, and gasoline for those who have cars or vehicles. Parents economize on children’s weekly monetary allowances. Online classes helped save time and energy by eliminating the need for travel to and from school. In the study, Burton (2019) noted that learning is most effective when pupils actively engage with new material through discussion with others, critical thinking, and self-reflective understanding of their own learning processes. As Maier (2020) said, following the decision-making phase, specific strategies are then developed and implemented. According to the results of their qualitative interviews with TA providers, Le and colleagues suggest that this process is most successful when TA plans are flexible and individualized, build upon current skills and competencies, and strengthen collaborative relationships. Others have echoed these ideas, calling for a collaborative approach to TA implementation in which the specific roles of TA providers are well-defined and complement the needs, current resources, and capaci-

ties of TA recipients that were defined during the decision-making phase. Table 6 exhibits the responses on the extent of self-learning module utilization in the Arts learning component. It can be seen that teachers do appreciate learner’s performance on Arts learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings (4.49); ensures that feedback based on the learner’s performance immediately on the fol-

lowing week (4.41); collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished (4.34); extra work sheets and supplemental learning materials necessary Art competencies per quarter are provided (4.24) and SLM for Arts Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter are given (4.20). This can be construed as teachers exhibiting very extensive utilization of SLMs in the Arts.

Table 6. Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization in Music

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Distributes SLM for Music Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter	4.20	Very Extensive
2	Provides extra worksheets and supplemental learning materials necessary for Music Grade 6 competencies per quarter	4.24	Very Extensive
3	Ensures collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished	4.34	Very Extensive
4	Provides feedback based on the learner’s performance immediately on the following week	4.41	Very Extensive
5	Appreciates learner’s performance on Music learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings	4.49	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.33	Very Extensive

Similarly, Katz and Wandersman, as cited by Leung et.al (2019), have suggested that process and outcome evaluations should be used to assess quality, reach, dosage, and recipient satisfaction, and that stakeholders should also plan for longer-term outcome evaluations. Lessons learned from these efforts can then be applied to enhance self-learning efforts as part of a broader, continuous quality improvement plan. However, the process of creating an actual field of study related to evidence-based technical assistance remains in its early stages. Moreover, a report examines community feedback to shed light on the impact that learning modules have on place-based programs for people in disadvantaged communities. Focusing on how modules can shape practices, expand stakeholder knowledge, and enhance stakeholder net-

works, it offers guidelines for future TA investments (Smith, 2019). Yazejian et.al (2019) said that a large national technical assistance learning module in Music and Arts and Sports in the US provides TA to Head Start regions to help strengthen their use of implementation science frameworks. In the administration of TA to regions, the centre has used a 'co-creation' model. The paper describes the co-creative TA approach, including the level of dosage (frequency and duration) provided, and interim outcomes achieved. Analyses revealed that the TA providers were successful in providing co-created TA and that interim outcomes, including trust, mutual accountability, and some integration of implementation science concepts into ongoing regional work, were achieved. Furthermore, the TA providers successfully delivered

TA that was perceived by both observers and participants as being participant-centered and tailored to their specific settings and needs. Limitations include a small sample size that was selected based on interest and readiness to en-

gage in TA, and descriptive analyses that did not permit claims of causality. The promising co-creation approach warrants further exploration and may offer guidance to others designing technical assistance.

Table 7. Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization in Physical Education

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Distributes SLM for Physical Education Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter	4.22	Very Extensive
2	Provides extra performance tasks and performance activity materials necessary for PE Grade 6 competencies per quarter	4.27	Very Extensive
3	Ensures collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished based on learners' needs and outputs	4.41	Very Extensive
4	Provides feedback based on the learner's performance tasks immediately in the following week and provides further coaching in learning	4.23	Very Extensive
5	Appreciates learner's performance outputs on PE learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings and feedback	4.46	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.31	Very Extensive

Table 7 presents the extent of self-learning module utilization in Physical Education. It can be seen that teachers utilizes SLMs in PE exhibits very extensive practice in terms of appreciating learner's performance outputs on PE learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings and feedback (4.48); collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and performance tasks are accomplished based on learners needs and outputs (4.41); extra performance tasks and performance activity materials necessary for PE Grade 6 competencies per quarter are provided (4.27); providing feedback based on the learner's performance tasks immediately on the following week and provides further coaching in learning (4.23) and SLM for Physical Education Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter are distributed. This implies that teachers utilize SLMs in PE in a very extensive (4.31) manner.

The key to the effective utilization of learning modules is to help learners, rather than solving problems for them. The primary purpose of providing learning modules by the School Division is to ensure that School-Based Management is implemented in the schools, as this is mandated by law, the R.A. 9155. Schools' divisions must ensure that schools are provided with the appropriate, relevant, and timely assistance to support continuous improvement, helping them achieve a higher level of SBM practice every time. In a similar manner, the purpose of the Regions in providing Technical Assistance to School Divisions should also ensure that they are able to support their schools in practicing SBM. Technical Assistance, in the form of allowing the utilization of self-learning modules, aims to enable the Regions to provide support and guidance to the School Divisions. The School Divisions, in turn, will assist their respective schools in

achieving continuous improvement in leadership management, thereby enabling schools as organizations to become more self-reliant and self-sustaining within their respective communities. Technical Assistance aims to provide broad-based capacity-building opportunities to the school, ensuring the effective delivery of services and improving learning outcomes. Technical Assistance complements the conduct of monitoring and evaluation. It aids in tracking the progress and results, and helps address concerns and enhance performance (Lauer, Christopher, Firpo-Triplett, Buchting, 2014, as cited by Magcanas, 2019).

Table 8 presents the extent of self-learning module utilization in the Health Sector. It can be

seen that learners' performance on Health learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings was appreciated (4.45); distribution of SLM for Health Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter (4.24); feedback based on the learner's performance immediately on the following week is provided (4.23); extra activity learning sheets and supplemental reading materials necessary for Health Grade 6 competencies per quarter were provided (4.21) and collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and written tasks are accomplished based on desired competencies are done (4.21). This implies that teachers extensively utilize self-learning modules in the Health Learning component.

Table 8. Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization in Health

No.	Statements	Mean	DI
1	Distributes SLM for Health Grade 6 based on the budget of work per quarter	4.24	Very Extensive
2	Provides extra activity learning sheets and supplemental reading materials necessary for Health Grade 6 competencies per quarter	4.21	Very Extensive
3	Ensures collections and retrieval of SLMs are complete and written tasks are accomplished based on desired competencies	4.21	Very Extensive
4	Provides feedback based on the learner's performance immediately on the following week	4.23	Very Extensive
5	Appreciates learner's performance on Health learning competencies per quarter through qualitative and quantitative ratings	4.45	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.26	Very Extensive

Pui, et. Al. (2021) said that many public-school districts are exploring performance pay as a means to improve administrator and teacher productivity and recruit more qualified teachers. Technical assistance, which involves training in areas that aid schools or districts in program design and implementation, can play a vital role in tackling these issues, especially if the assistance deals not only with necessary topics for quality programs such as helping a school de-

termine fair and quality measures of educator performance, developing data systems, and calculating bonus awards but also integrates tactics to ensure that lessons learned from training are sustained over time and embedded in the organization's culture and systems. Moreover, these tactics ensure that key lessons for quality program operation are not only understood by school practitioners at the time of delivery, but persist throughout the duration of program

implementation. Table 9 provides a summary of the extent of self-learning module utilization in terms of music (4.33), arts (4.33), physical education (4.31), and health (4.31) learning components. This provides implications that teachers in Davao de Oro extensively utilize learning modules in these learning components in MAPEH.

Table 9. Summary on the Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization

No.	SLM Utilization	Mean	DI
1	Music	4.33	Very Extensive
2	Arts	4.33	Very Extensive
3	Physical Education	4.31	Very Extensive
4	Health	4.26	Very Extensive
Overall Mean		4.31	Very Extensive

3.3. *Significant Relationship Between the Technical Assistance Provided by and Self-Learning Modules Utilization In MAPEH*— It can be observed that Pearson’s correlation showed a significant correlation between the ex-

tent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers ($r = 0.869$; $p < .001$) and the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in the Davao de Oro Schools Division.

Table 10. Significant Relationship Between Technical Assistance Provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and SLM Utilization by Teachers

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Technical Assistance Provision	0.869	<0.001	Significant	Reject H_0 *

[*] Significant at $p < .05$.

Table 10 gives empirical evidence to support that the posed null hypothesis stating there is no significant relationship between extent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and Teachers’ extent of utilization of self-Learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division must be rejected, thus, can be said that extent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and Teachers’ extent of utilization of self-Learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division is significantly correlated. T.A. often emphasizes the importance of a structured approach by the provider, including the specification of measurable goals linked to concrete ac-

tion steps, the provision of continuous feedback, the improvement of feedback loops, and the discussion of progress to track activities. Lastly, there is an emphasis on empowerment and motivation. This has led to the development of confidence, and efficacy is recognized as a fundamental ingredient in achieving positive outcomes (Kapur, 2018, as cited by Olson, 2020). In the Philippine setting, San Antonio (2020) noted that DepEd Teachers integrate technical assistance to improve the delivery of basic education services. The Department of Education launched DepEd Teachers, an online program featuring episodes that focus on steps and initiatives for overcoming the challenges in providing education in the new normal, during the mid-

year In-Service Training (INSET) Week from December 14 to 18, 2020. The program aims to address confusion and doubts about the Department’s curriculum, instruction, and assessment initiatives. This initiative is a contribution from the Curriculum and Instruction strand to support the Department of Education’s efforts in communicating with various stakeholders. It serves as a mechanism for providing technical assistance to the field as we adapt to the new normal in basic education (Secretary Leonor Magtolis-Briones, 2020). A qualitative analysis of interviews with experienced TA providers has suggested a continuum of practice anchored at each end by approaches termed content-driven and relationship-based. Moreover, content-driven approaches focus on information transfer and referral, whereas relationship-based approaches center on facilitating behavior and systems change.

3.4. *The Domains of Technical Assistance Significantly Influence the Extent of Self-Learning Modules Utilization in MAPEH*—Table 11 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence of the extent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers on the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division. All indicators of Technical Assistance provided, namely coaching (0.002), guiding (0.002), and empowering (0.004), indicate statistically significant influence on the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules by teachers in the MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division. This provides empirical evidence to show that the indicators of Technical Assistance provided directly influence teachers’ extent of utilization of self-learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in the Davao de Oro Schools Division during the pandemic.

Table 11. Regression Coefficient Analysis on the Indicators of TA Provision that Significantly Influence Teachers’ Utilization of SLMs

Model	B	Beta	SE	p	Decision
H ₀ (Intercept)	4.467			0.044	< .001
H ₁ (Intercept)	0.319		0.136	0.056	
Coaching	0.212	0.241	0.045	0.002	Reject H ₀
Guiding	0.113	0.130	0.052	0.002	Reject H ₀
Empowering	0.029	0.025	0.118	0.004	Reject H ₀

Note. $R^2 = .784$, $F(3, N - 1) = 45.356$, $p < .001$.

Meanwhile, the R² value of 0.784 suggests that the Technical Assistance provided in Davao de Oro accounts for 78.4 % of the variance of teachers’ utilization of SLMs. This provides empirical evidence that the variability of teachers’ utilization of SLMs can be accounted and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under indicators of Technical Assistance provided in Davao de Oro. Additionally, the F-value displays the sum of squares, given that regression was the model, and the Residual is the error. The F-value (45.356) and F-statistic are signifi-

cant, $p < .001$. This indicates that the model is a significantly better predictor of teachers’ extent of SLM utilization. Moreover, Olson et al. (2020) added that in recent years, TA provision has become a common component of the implementation process for a wide variety of youth-focused federal, state, and community-based initiatives, spawning a small but growing body of literature focused on evaluating and identifying the characteristics of effective TA. There has been growing interest in studying how to utilize training and TA to support the implementation

of specific evidence-based practices, as well as an emerging dialogue about how best to utilize TA to improve the overall functioning of larger organizations and systems. Moreover, there has been consistent interest in ensuring that TA systems themselves are based on comparative effectiveness research. Furthermore, the authors noted that the TA must be administered at a sufficient dosage. Recent evidence suggests that long-term, ongoing TA is associated with better outcomes than one-shot, time-limited efforts. Second, TA should encompass a mixture of intensive support (e.g., on-site consultation and engagement in in-person and virtual learning communities) that provides opportunities for experiential learning through hands-on demonstrations and off-site check-ins via telephone and electronic communications, allowing for cost-efficient and frequent contacts. Third, TA activities benefit from a collaborative approach in which TA providers offer expert guidance in specific substantive areas and also form working relationships with various stakeholders, including policy-makers, program administrators, implementers, and service recipients. Finally, recent papers have suggested that there are benefits associated with a proactive approach to TA, in which TA providers anticipate stakeholder needs and respond to those needs in a timely, positive, and ongoing way. Proactive TA typically builds upon stakeholder strengths with the ultimate goal of improving systems-level capacity and high-quality implementation (Olson et al., 2020).

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the results of the analyzed data, discusses implications, and draws conclusions. Findings are based on the posed statement of the problem; conclusions are drawn from the findings generated; and recommendations are based on the implications of the discussions.

4.1. Findings—The following are the study's findings, based on the results presented, analysis, and discussions. Davao de Oro Schools exhibited a pervasive extent of technical assistance provided by School Heads and Master teachers in terms of coaching (4.27), guiding (4.35), and empowerment (4.33), suggesting very effective management. Davao de Oro Schools' extent of self-learning modules utilization in terms of music (4.33), arts (4.33), physical education (4.31), and health (4.31) learning components suggests that teachers extensively utilize learning modules in these learning components in MAPEH. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers ($r = 0.869$; $p < .001$) and the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in the Davao de Oro Schools Division. All indicators of Technical Assistance provided, namely coaching (0.002), guiding (0.002), and empowering (0.004), indicate statistically significant influence on the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules by teachers in the MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division.

4.2. Conclusion—Given the findings of the study presented, the following are conclusions, to wit; Davao de Oro Schools exhibited extensive technical assistance in terms of coaching, guidance, and empowerment, suggesting very effective management. The extent of self-learning module utilization in Davao de Oro Schools, particularly in music, arts, physical education, and health learning components, suggests that teachers utilize learning modules extensively in these areas of the MAPEH curricu-

lum. Pearson's correlation showed a significant correlation between the extent of Technical Assistance provided by School Heads and Master Teachers and the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules in MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division. All indicators of Technical Assistance, namely coaching, guiding, and empowering, indicate a statistically significant influence on the extent of utilization of self-learning Modules by teachers in the MAPEH learning components in Davao de Oro Schools Division. The Technical Assistance (TA) Model theory by Lee, Anthony, Bronheim, and Holland (2014) is significant for both providing technical assistance and utilizing self-learning modules because it offers a structured framework to enhance knowledge transfer, promote active participation from recipients, and foster skill development, ultimately leading to more effective and efficient learning experiences in both settings. The Lee, Anthony, Bronheim, and Holland (2014) model is crucial in delivering technical assistance (TA) effectively. It promotes active engagement, enhanced knowledge transfer, and action planning, encouraging recipients to apply their learning. The model also aids in designing self-learning modules that encourage active learning, focus on skill development, and improve effectiveness. By incorporating principles from the model, modules can be designed with interactive activities and practical applications, enhancing the effectiveness of the learning experience. Thus, the model serves as a valuable theoretical foundation for designing dynamic, interactive, and successful TA and self-learning resources.

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4.3. *Recommendation*—Based on the study's findings, several recommendations are proposed.: Public School District Supervisors in Davao de Oro are encouraged to investigate additional factors that may influence teachers' pedagogical development, particularly regarding the effective use and maximization of self-learning modules within the context of alternative delivery modes. These insights could serve as valuable policy inputs for future educational strategies. School Administrators in Davao de Oro are advised to continue and strengthen their efforts in promoting the effective implementation and utilization of self-learning modules among teachers. They should also encourage their respective schools to adopt similar practices and pursue ongoing professional development. Furthermore, exploring other variables that may impact school performance and instructional effectiveness could provide a more comprehensive understanding, and such findings should be integrated into school improvement initiatives. For Future Researchers, it is recommended to delve deeper into the underlying processes and mechanisms by which teachers employ self-learning modules to enhance their pedagogical skills. Investigating these aspects through empirical studies could shed light on how these practices contribute to professional growth. Additionally, incorporating these insights into the planning, implementation, and evaluation phases of instructional strategies can lead to a more effective integration of self-learning modules into teaching practices.

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